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Analysis of passive acoustic in situ observing systems in the Arctic Ocean using ARCMAP

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The Integrated Arctic Observing System project has conducted a survey of Arctic in situ observing systems and in situ and remote sensing data collections. Based on questionnaires from this survey we have developed ARCMAP (<https://arcmmap.nersc.no>), a user-friendly web system for collecting and maintaining information about Arctic in situ observing systems and data collections. The information is stored in a database allowing easy generation of statistics, for example on spatial and temporal coverage, parameters observed and targeted application areas, nationality of owners, funding sources and periods and maturity of data storage and management. We have extracted information about systems observing ocean sound and located in the Arctic. We also compared with other repositories of metadata for acoustic observing systems. The ARCMAP database currently has 11 occurrences of systems containing ocean sound and provides assessment information, e.g. on data storage, in addition to basic metadata, e.g. location and time coverage. This study focuses on sustainability of the observing systems, and it is found that the typical system is focused, project based, funded at the national level and has non-advanced routines for data storage and management, in good agreement with the common view about Arctic observing systems.

1. INTRODUCTION

Sound is important for many marine animals in their communication, for predator and prey detection, and for some like the odontocete whales, echolocation is important. The Arctic is an important habitat for many marine animal species utilizing sound. The region is experiencing rapid change, with an overall decrease in sea ice extent during the last decades as the most prominent manifestation (PAME, 2019). The increased accessibility caused by opening up the Arctic may potentially intensify underwater noise due to commercial vessels, fishing, community re-supply, mining, tourist and pleasure craft traffic, military exercises and oil and gas extraction activities (seismic air guns, drilling, and construction). A comprehensive overview of baseline passive acoustic data is therefore needed as a reference for future studies of change in the acoustic environment in the Arctic. Furthermore, the Arctic is relatively little investigated in general and largely acoustically pristine, so more research efforts are needed. The comparably fewer observations and observation programs in the Arctic than elsewhere is mainly due to the harsh logistical conditions. In addition, observations are mostly process oriented, based on project funding, thus making them heterogeneous and largely unavailable outside the research community. In this regard it is positive that ocean sound has now become a mature Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS) *essential ocean variable* (Howe et al., 2019).

In order to improve and augment the monitoring of the Arctic Ocean and upon which decisions can be taken, there is a need for an extensive, harmonized and sustainable acoustic observation network. Presently, the observing systems are scattered and utilize different standards (IQOE, 2021). Howe et al. (2019) recommend that multipurpose acoustic systems be brought into operational status for monitoring the polar seas.

Information about existing observing systems in the Arctic, including passive acoustic networks, is scattered among multiple databases and websites. Therefore, we developed ARCMAP which is a user-friendly web system for collecting and maintaining information about Arctic in situ observing systems and data collections. A number of relevant metadata- and databases already exist, all with their specific purposes. A unique feature of ARCMAP is its focus on information regarding sustainability of the observing systems. For a selection of meta-databases we have performed a simple assessment with an aim to determine their capabilities with regard to acoustic observations (Section 2).

ARCMAP was developed as a contribution to the EU Horizon 2020 project Integrated Arctic Observing System (INTAROS), whose aim is to create a roadmap towards implementation of an integrated Arctic observing system (Tjernström et al., 2020). The present development (Section 3) may thus be seen as a stepping-stone on the road towards a complete delivery system for acoustic data in the Arctic. The major part of this work provides an example of extraction of and interpretation of information from ARCMAP with regard to ocean sound. Through a search in the database for systems having Ocean sound as an observation parameter, records were extracted for further analysis, as described in Section 4. The results are discussed in Section 5 and concluded in Section 6.

1. BRIEF REVIEW OF SELECTED METADATA AND DATA SYSTEMS

There exist a few websites for viewing metadata on acoustic observing systems that we are aware of. We follow the definitions of Tjernström et al. (2020): “An *in-situ observing system* consists of a data collection component (infrastructure) and a data management component (e-infrastructure). The data collection component is comprised of multiple sensors either belonging to a common fixed platform (such as cabled system, sea floor installation, mooring), which can be a single unit or a collection of units forming a network, or installed on a non-stationary platform (ship, aircraft, gliders, floats, ice buoys) [...]” In Table 1 we list some key information on four in-situ observing systems including ARCMAP (the latter presented in detail in Section 3).

The International Quiet Ocean Experiment ([IQOE](#)) website provides a menu point ‘Acoustic observing systems’ providing the user with a simple to use interface for getting an overview of passive acoustic monitoring sites Worldwide. The user has the option to select display of either autonomous or cabled systems. Then one can select up to 24 different information fields that are mostly of type free text. The results are then displayed in a table. No other filtering or export options are available.

Table 1. Overview of sites holding information of acoustic observing systems. i) as of 23 August 2021. ii) in addition there are 2-3 fields per observed variable. iii) counting all observing systems. iv) 14 are of type text, 26 of type single or multiple choice. v) 115 systems in total, 11 systems observing ocean sound.

Site	URL	Area	Discipline / theme	No. of information fields	No. of systems ⁱ
IQOE	https://www.iqoe.org/systems	Global	Acoustics	24	109
CAFF PAM	https://geokart.npolar.no/Html5Viewer/index.html?viewer=ArcticPAM	Arctic	Acoustics	19	339
SIOS	https://sios-svalbard.org/sios-ri-catalogue	Svalbard	All themes	12 ⁱⁱ	261 ⁱⁱⁱ
ARCMAP	https://arcmmap.nersc.no	Arctic	All themes	47 ^{iv}	115/11 ^v

The Conservation of Arctic Flora and Fauna (**CAFF**) working group under Arctic Council leads a program on Pan-Arctic Passive Acoustic Monitoring (PAM). The CAFF PAM Metadata Database hosted by the Norwegian Polar Institute contains records of Passive Acoustic Monitoring (PAM) instruments deployed across the Arctic. A handy Graphical User Interface (GUI) allows zooming in on a map and selecting locations of interest. Multiyear and one-year sites are marked with separate colors. The subsequent table that is generated displays 19 fields, of which the majority contains text. Filtering and export options with a large flexibility for the user is implemented.

Svalbard Integrated Arctic Earth Observing System (**SIOS**) maintains an Observation Facilities Catalogue holds observation facilities (i.e. instruments or collections thereof) collecting data on and near Svalbard. The description of observing systems follows the WMO standards as far as possible, in order to make entries unambiguous and interoperable internationally. A GUI facilitates the search operation, allowing for queries combining multiple criteria, among others, facility name, institution, project, and observed variable. Searching for ‘ocean sound’ or ‘ambient noise’ yields a few hits, which may imply that few acoustic observing systems in fjords and coastal regions of Svalbard have been registered so far.

ARCMAP maintains a database of in situ observing systems across multiple spheres (e.g. sea ice, ocean land, atmosphere) in the Arctic. We note that ARCMAP holds several information fields on assessment information that the other systems do not, therefore it has the highest number (47) for this parameter (Table 1).

For completeness we also include some widely used sites for data delivery, as data sampled by the observing systems should after processing and quality control be published in an open data repository.

PANGAEA is a database with global coverage currently holding more than 400,000 datasets from all disciplinary themes. However, selecting the ocean theme and searching for ‘sound’ yields only 221 results and does not seem to discern between active and passive acoustics, phrases as ‘sound velocity’, ‘echo sounder’ and location descriptions containing ‘sound’ in a name. Limiting the search by such phrases (preceding a string by a minus sign ‘-’), reduces the number of hits, but a universal way to isolate only passive acoustic measurements was not found. On the other hand, searching for ‘soundscape’ yields 20 unique hits.

The Norwegian Marine Data Center (**NMDC**) holds information on or links to marine datasets provided by mainly Norwegian institutions with emphasis on Norwegian waters, including Svalbard. A free search on ‘acoustic’ yields 81 hits, including echo sounder, sonar and ADCP measurements, whereas ‘ambient noise’ yields 6 data sets.

The **INTAROS Data Catalog** is a metadata catalog on Arctic datasets covering all disciplinary themes currently holding 137 datasets generated by the INTAROS project. A search yields 5 data sets tagged with ‘passive acoustics’ of which 4 also are tagged ‘ambient sound’.

EMODNET has for each of seven disciplinary themes, created a gateway to a range of data archives managed by a number of international data providing organisations. Selecting the physics theme and

‘underwater noise’ yields four hits only. For the biology theme a free search for ‘acoustic’ or ‘sound’ yielded 17 or 18 hits, respectively, with minor overlaps. The majority were recordings of mammal sound, but also some data sets dealt with active acoustics.

The Norwegian Polar Data Centre ([NPDC](#)) hosts data of the Norwegian Polar Institute from the Arctic and Antarctic. Free searches for ‘acoustic’, ‘sound’ or ‘noise’ yields 10, 14 and 3 hits, respectively (out of 260 total). Again, a large fraction consists of active acoustics and also non-marine data sets.

IQOE also provides an [Acoustic Data Portal](#) linking to 13 national or project sites holding passive acoustic data, of which several also contain general ocean data. To survey all those is beyond the scope of the present paper.

The [SIOS Data Portal](#) links to 83006 datasets. A search for ‘acoustic’ or ‘sound’ yields 12 and 10 hits, respectively, mostly for data dealing with active acoustics.

The Open Portal to Underwater Sound ([OPUS](#)) is under development by the Alfred Wegener Institute (IQOE, 2020). According to the information on the site “[t]he portal will give access to HAFOS, FRAM and PALAOA recordings by audio and synchronized spectral visualizations at staggered temporal resolution to enjoy underwater (night-)life“.

Summarizing, we have found that, except for the dedicated sound sites IQOE and CAFF, none of the data or metadata bases utilize ‘ocean sound’ as a keyword or observed variable. ARCMAP, as a recent development, has implemented it, and searches for this essential ocean variable thus become straightforward and yield unambiguous results. Our exploratory searches in selected data systems indicated that only a relatively small fraction of datasets on passive acoustics has been published in these open data bases. Further effort is therefore needed to advance production chains ensuring increased availability of passive acoustic data for science, public and private sector.

2. DESIGN OF ARCMAP

The INTAROS project has conducted a survey of Arctic in situ observing systems, in situ and remote sensing data collections (Ludwigsen et al., 2018; Tjernström et al., 2020). Based on the questionnaires from this survey we have developed a user-friendly web system - ARCMAP - for collecting and maintaining information about Arctic in situ observing systems and data collections.

ARCMAP enables users to register and maintain information about Arctic in situ observing systems and data collections (Hamre et al., 2020). The information is stored in a database allowing easy generation of statistics, for example spatial and temporal coverage, parameters observed and targeted application areas, nationality of owners, funding sources and periods and maturity of data management. The [ARCMAP website](#) consists of three sub-sites: (1) A survey site for users to enter and update information on their assessed systems, (2) a client site where registered users can view and extract data about their own systems, (3) a statistics site generating plots on a daily basis, such as histograms of number of systems for various spheres, each for atmosphere, ocean and land, respectively.

Through the survey part of ARCMAP, new observing systems and data collections can be easily registered. The survey consists of six parts whose content can be stored individually, to ease the task for the user. Responses to the questions of the survey are mapped to fields in the ARCMAP database. Fields containing selections of single or multiple choice are used as the basis for the statistics generated by the system. The fields containing text provide information such as names of the observing systems and contact persons for them and their datasets, names for organizations coordinating the operation of the observing systems, as well as information elaborating the responses in the selection choice fields. Some text fields, such as names of the observing systems are used to label statistics plots and tables, while the majority is used in the assessment of observing capacities and gaps (Tjernström et al., 2020).

The home page of ARCMAP provides a GUI where the location and some key characteristics of the in situ systems are presented on a dynamic map. The Leaflet Javascript library was used to implement the map presenting the location and selected characteristics on the ARCMAP home page. In this interactive map, an interactive overview map in polar stereographic projection has been developed. Each observing system is plotted, and a short information “bubble” is revealed when an observing system marker is clicked. A clustering method has been implemented to reduce the number of markers displayed at once at a given magnification. Clusters are shown as filled circles with a number within, denoting the number of observing systems the cluster includes. By clicking on a cluster, the map zooms in and the observing systems for that

cluster are displayed, either as individual systems (shown as markers) or as smaller groups (clusters) of systems. Thus, clusters can include other clusters, which are opened as the user zooms into the map. Figures 1 and 2 show two examples of the geographic distribution of observing systems captured in the ARCMAP survey database.

Figure 1. Overview map of observing systems in ARCMAP. Clusters of observing systems are shown as color-filled circles. When holding the mouse pointer over a circle, the area that the cluster covers is shown as a blue area. Single observation systems are shown as blue pin markers. When clicking on a blue pin marker, an information bubble is displayed.

Figure 2. Zooming in the overview map. When clicking on a cluster marker, the map will zoom in to display the observing systems covered by that cluster. Clusters can include other clusters as well as single observing systems.

4. INFORMATION RETRIEVED FROM ARCMAP

In this paper we use ARCMAP to obtain information about the observing systems that include ‘ocean sound’ as an observed variable. Out of 115 assessed observing systems eleven systems contained ‘ocean sound’. For the analysis we used the graphical and statistical functions of Microsoft Excel. In the following we provide some examples of information extracted for these observing systems, where we have limited

our study to system characteristics of categorical type. We list the system characteristic title, its categories (response alternatives) and provide a brief interpretation when possible. For instance, the analysis revealed that many of the assessed acoustic systems appear to have poorly developed data storage capability. However, as the database is in a build-up phase, one should have in mind that any inference based on only 11 samples can only be tentative.

- **System category.** Multiple choice, 6 categories.

This system characteristic field provides information on the broader purpose of the observing system.

Options:

Broad network (it includes a broad range of interdisciplinary observations and projects)

Focused network (is confined to specific themes or disciplines)

Commercial network (provides observational data for profit)

Operational network (feeding observations into weather service and forecast entities)

Resource-extraction network (conducts monitoring or baseline observations specifically for planned or ongoing resource extraction activities)

Distributed data (from many local networks)

Figure 3. Bar plot of the characteristic ‘System category’

From Fig. 3 we observe that the majority of systems (9) are purely focused, i.e. confined to specific themes or disciplines. Only one observing system is characterized as a broad network, including a broad range of interdisciplinary observations and projects, whereas one system is registered as both focused and broad. None of the remaining four categories were selected. There is a clear tendency for the acoustic observing systems to be focused, which is in general agreement with the general view that observing systems have a scientific motivation and are temporally and geographically limited.

- **Scientific support.** Single choice, 5 choices.

Scientific support captures the extent and quality of human resources available to maintain the system, i.e. a key prerequisite for sustainability. From Fig. 4a we see that the typical response is 3 - “Technical expertise is available to support operation of the observing system” (5 responses). In general responses spread over all categories, and category 5 holding the best sustainability measure scores second highest (3 responses). This may lead to the conclusion that the situation is over all satisfactory with respect to available personnel resources.

- **Funding support.** Single choice. 5 choices

Funding support (Fig. 4b) seeks to measure the level of stability and sufficiency of available financial resources, again a key prerequisite for sustainability of operation. The typical response here is 2 - “Project based funding support available” (6 responses), with category 3 as number two - “as 2 +expectation of follow-on funding”.

- **Funding source.** Multiple choice, 4 categories

This system characteristic is related to the previous one in that also the international level of the funding body can be relevant for sustainability. Typically, sustainability is likely to be ensured the higher the

international level. We see (Fig. 5) that the majority of systems receives national funding (8 solely, 2 in combination with international, EU and/or private funding); only one has EU as its main funding body.

Categories:

- 1) None (No scientific or technical support is available)
- 2) Minimal scientific support required to sustain the program is available, sufficient to maintain the measurement program at present state, but not in case of major failure or breakdown of the observing system
- 3) Technical expertise is available to support operation of the observing system (to ensure continuation of the measurements including maintenance and replacement of sensors, and secure data storage)
- 4) As in (3) + at least two technical experts to secure the measurement program operation
- 5) As in (4) + research and development to ensure that the observing system is based on state-of-the-art technology

Categories:

- 1) None (No dedicated funding support is evident for the measurement program)
- 2) Project based funding support available (there is dedicated funding support, but it is tied to a project and therefore not continuous)
- 3) As in (2) + expectation of follow-on funding (there is a reasonable expectation that funding will be renewed, for the same project or for other projects that may have slightly different focus but similar set of measurements)
- 4) As in (3) + not dependent on a single investigator or funding line
- 5) Sustained infrastructure support through e.g. national infrastructure programs which are stable and unlikely to be removed in the foreseeable future

Figure 4. Bar plot of the characteristics (a) Scientific support and (b) Funding support

Figure 5. Bar diagram of the characteristic ‘Funding source’

- **System standard.** Multiple choice, 5 categories.

Here the respondents were asked *Is any international/community standard implemented?* The typical response was ‘No’ (9 counts) as seen in Fig. 6a, i.e. no community standards are implemented, a characteristic generally associated with a low degree of sustainability.

- **Discovery service.** Multiple choice, 10 categories.

An important property of an observing system is that its data are findable (the ‘F’ in the FAIR-principles; Wilkinson *et al.*, 2016). Hence, the respondents were asked if their system supported any discovery service. Perhaps not surprising, the typical reply was ‘None’ (6 counts), with ‘I don’t know’ ranking as number two (3 counts; Fig. 6b). This negative result may also reflect that the survey was responded to by scientists, without any involvement of technical personnel that would probably be necessary for this question.

Figure 6. Pie charts of the characteristics (a) ‘System standard’ and (b) ‘Discovery service’. In (a) two unselected alternatives were “Yes, it applies to all collections, but it may vary from dataset to dataset” and “Other”. In (b) six unselected options were “OGC CSW”, “OGC GeoSPARQL”, “OpenSearch”, “OAI-PMH”, “CKAN”, “FTP”.

- **Data storage.** Multiple choice, 7 categories.

Again, to achieve sustainability, data needs to be stored in a reliable manner. All responses contain the option ‘Institutional’, most in combination with ‘Personal’ (n=5) and 4 in singularity (Fig. 7a). It is noteworthy that the definition of ‘Personal’ in this study explicitly excludes explicitly the ‘Institutional’ option, so it is reasonable to think that respondents have had in mind a personal duplication of the institutional data sets. Such apparent ambiguity in the category definitions blur the interpretation of responses and it will be natural to eliminate them as far as possible in future updates of the survey.

- **Data access.** Single choice, 9 categories.

Data access measures the ease with which data will be available for any user. From Fig. 7b we see again a clear tendency that ‘data is available on request to trusted users (Data validation is not yet completed, but data may be available to beta-users for testing.)’ (n=7). I.e., data access is typically dependent of some personal interaction by the data originating person or institution.

Categories:

(Inst) Data are stored in an institutional/departmental repository

(Distr) Data are stored in distributed repositories (institutional or other)

(Pers) Data are not stored in any institutional repository, but in a personal repository such as hard-disk, computer, notebook, etc.

Data are stored in a national repository according to legal constraints on their location (a specific repository is compulsory for certain data)

Instpers = Inst & Pers

InstpersO = Inst & Pers & Other

Data are stored in a national repository without legal constraints on their location (no repository is compulsory for any data)

Data are stored in an international repository (O) Other

Categories:

1, **A**) Unknown

2, **B**) Data is available on request to trusted users (Data validation is not yet completed, but data may be available to beta-users for testing.)

3, **C**) Data is available on supervised request through originator (Data is ready to be given to users without any restrictions on academic usage. Users must contact the data originator to get the data)

4) Data is available on automated request through originator (Data is ready to be given to users without any restrictions on academic usage. Users can get the data by requesting it from a publicly accessible site.)

5) Data and documentation are available on supervised request through originator (Data and appropriate documentation are publicly available for academic use through the data provider)

6, **D**) Data and documentation are available on automated request through originator (Data and appropriate documentation are publicly available for academic use through a publicly accessible site)

7) Data and documentation are available on automated request through originator and recognized data portal such as Copernicus Climate Change Data Portal, NDACC Portal or NOAA's National Centers for Environmental Information

8) As 7 + source data, code and metadata available upon request allowing reprocessing of the full measurement series.

9) As 8 + no restrictions apply (there are no restrictions on use or reuse of the data, metadata or code and all aspects are made available free of charge.

(a)

(b)

Figure 7. Bar plot of the characteristics (a) 'Data storage' and (b) 'Data access'.

- **Long term data preservation.** Single choice, 5 categories

This system characteristic picks up how the data is archived and the level of advancement of the archiving infrastructure. Although the typical response is 'None' (n=4), the responses are more evenly spread out on the first three categories (Fig. 8). A fairly high score (n=3) for category 3 indicates that at least part of the community reached a standard indicating that "each version archived at an institutional level on at least two media".

● **Combined properties**

A further step in the analysis could be to look at all characteristics in combination. For instance, clustering techniques or machine learning may be invoked to find out whether the data cluster around certain typical patterns in the multivariate space. As an example, with our small sample, we have plotted two

Categories:

- 1, **A)** None (No archiving system in apparent use for the data collections)
- 2, **B)** Local archive retained by data collector which may be used to retrieve data on an ad hoc request basis, but is dependent upon the data collector or a single small group
- 3, **C)** Each version archived at an institutional level on at least two media (Data archival is transferred from the data collector to an institutionally maintained archive and formalized, stored on at least two media in two distinct locations)
- 4) Data, raw data and metadata are archived at a recognized data repository, national archive or international repository
- 5) As 4 + all versions of measurement series, metadata, software etc. retained, indexed and accessible upon request.

Figure 8. Bar plot of the characteristic ‘Long term data preservation’.

characteristics against each other and observe the implied bivariate distribution. In this case we plot the fields Funding support and Scientific support against each other. In Fig. 9 we see that the mode (n=3) of the distribution is at (3, 3) which decodes to: “Technical expertise is available to support operation of the observing system (to ensure continuation of the measurements including maintenance and replacement of sensors, and secure data storage)” and “Project based funding support available (there is dedicated funding support, but it is tied to a project and therefore not continuous) + expectation of follow on funding (there is a reasonable expectation that funding will be renewed, for the same project or for other projects that may

Figure 9. Scatter plot of the characteristics ‘Funding support’ vs ‘Scientific support’. The scores are provided to the right of the dot symbols. Unnumbered dots have score = 1

have slightly different focus but similar set of measurements) “. For this case the mode coincides with that of the single characteristic ‘Scientific support’, whereas for ‘Funding support’ it is one step above the mode of the characteristic viewed in isolation. From Fig. 9 it can be seen that for ‘Funding support’ = 2 (Project based funding) ‘Scientific support’ spread out almost over the entire scale. Once stepping up one unit in

‘Funding support’, the values become centered around (3,3). A possible interpretation may be that for low funding the scientific resource is funded elsewhere. Whereas, when some more funding is secured, hiring of technical personnel tends to be prioritized.

5. DISCUSSION

By taking all the results obtained in Section 4 together, we may obtain a general characteristic of the typical Arctic observing system observing ‘ocean sound’. One simple way to do this - based on the 11 surveyed ones – may be to add together the individual modes of each distribution. By doing so, we can state that the typical Arctic observing system has the following characteristics:

- Observing networks are focused on specific themes or disciplines
- Technical expertise is available to ensure continuation of the measurements including maintenance and replacement of sensors, and secure data storage
- Observation networks are project based and supported by national funding
- No standard for data encoding is implemented
- Data are stored partly in institutional or distributed systems
- No data discovery service is implemented
- No archiving system is in apparent use for the data collections.
- Data is available on request to trusted users.

The sample of examined systems (n=11) is too small to draw any wide conclusion, but as several of its statements appear to be congruent with general views as expressed in the introductory section, we may nevertheless claim that the analysis provides quantitative evidence backing up the general views held by the observing community. It will be interesting to see if the results will be robust when the analysis is repeated with a more populated database. Analysis of a larger sample could also explore whether application of clustering techniques will have any merit.

When it comes to the specific system characteristics, such as ‘Scientific support’, its relatively high score (n=3) obtained for the “best” category (=5) together with a high score (=5) for the mode, make it stand out among the other characteristics. This indicates that the sustainability aspect is overall good regarding scientific support compared to the general state. Here we have assumed that the characteristic in consideration is at ordinal measure level, which is in general not the case. Some precautions should also be taken when interpreting the results. For instance, for characteristics such as ‘System standard’ and ‘Discovery service’ having high scores for categories as ‘No’, ‘None’ or ‘I do not know’ may indicate that the respondent did not understand the underlying questions. The typical respondent was a scientist, so in future revisions of the survey information that such questions be answered by technical experts should be added. Sporadic feedback to the designers also supports this view. Furthermore, for a characteristic like ‘Data storage’ the possibility of joint selection of two choices that by their definitions are mutually exclusive, should be avoided. Closer inspection of the scores of all the characteristics may provide further guidelines on revision of survey questions and response alternatives. Changing the alternatives for a question may invalidate previous responses. In such cases, the benefits of obtaining new information should be weighed against the effort needed to update already collected information.

The relatively low scores for the characteristics ‘Data storage’, ‘Data access’ and ‘Long term data preservation’ is also consistent with what was found in Section 2, that the investigated relevant data portals contained only a small fraction of passive acoustic data. The reason for this remains to be investigated. The apparent lack of fixed tags or keywords adds to this picture as free text searches using various sets of criteria seldom yield unique results. If database managers implement ‘ocean sound’ as a tag, it will be a step forward. Similarly, acousticians should report their data to the larger facilities.

6. CONCLUSION

ARCMAP has been designed as a user-friendly web system for collecting and maintaining information about Arctic in situ observing systems and data collections. It has also been demonstrated as an efficient tool to retrieve statistical information about Arctic acoustics observing systems regarding their sustainability. A preliminary conclusion based on the small sample (n=11) of surveyed Arctic observing

systems is that the typical system is focused, project based, funded nationally and has non-advanced routines for data storage and management, in agreement with the present general view. This result is based on the typical responses for each individual question independently.

Consistent with the statistical result, we also found that there are relatively few datasets on passive acoustics reported in the repositories such as PANGAEA or EMODNET. In addition, there are no unique search terms when searching for passive acoustic data. It is therefore recommended that databases holding acoustic data utilize the recently defined Essential Ocean Variable ‘ocean sound’ as a keyword, to ease searches and avoid ambiguities.

The meta-databases of IQOE and CAFF dedicated to acoustic observing systems can be valuable for further ingestion of data into ARCMAP, by identifying systems for assessment. It is also recommended that these and other relevant sites are considered for harvesting information to be utilized by ARCMAP and minimizing the effort for the responders.

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